

Gender Equality in Uzbekistan, Its Importance and Impact On a Developing Future

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Abstract

This article discusses the inequality between men and women in our country today, its importance and the positive impact of gender equality for the future of Uzbekistan. In addition, the work done by government agencies on this topic was studied.

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Introduction

Respect for women is an ancient value of the Uzbek people. The role of women in the history of great commanders, statesmen and great dynasties has been invaluable in our history. Among the women who left an indelible mark on the history of the peoples of Central Asia were Sitora Bonu (mother of Abu Ali Ibn Sino), Gavharshodbegim (mother of Mirzo Ulugbek), Saraymulkhanim (wife of Amir Temur), Kutluginigorkhanim (grandmother of Babur Mirza), Gulbadanbegim (Babur Babur). Hundreds of researches on the spiritual world of such holy women as Mirza's daughter), Wali Orifahon (mother of Bahauddin Naqshband), Robiya Balhi, Qurbonjon Dodho, Zebuniso, Nodirabegim, Anbar atin Uvaysi, their role in the social, political and military processes of that time and research has been done. We are proud to mention such famous women as Zulfiyakhanim, Sora Eshontorayeva, Tamarakhonim, Mukarrama Turgunbaeva, Saodat Kobulova, Fozila Sulaymonova, Muzayyana Alaviya, Buritosh Shodiyeva, who introduced the voice of the Uzbek people to the world in the recent past. In the words of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan IA Karimov, “.. There are many criteria in the world that reflect the prestige and cultural level of the state and society. But there is a criterion that clearly reflects the spiritual maturity of any nation and people, which is determined by the attitude of society to women. In this sense, it is safe to say that a nation that honors, respects, and upholds women will gain a reputation as a nation that demonstrates and affirms its high culture and noble values.”

Main part

Equality between women and men is guaranteed by the basic laws of many democracies, including the Constitution of Uzbekistan, as well as a number of international instruments, agreements, conventions and declarations concerning human rights. These include the UN Charter (June 26, 1945), the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (December 10, 1948), the Covenants on Civil and Political Rights, and the economic, social, and cultural rights adopted by the UN in 1966. international covenants, including many international agreements that constitute an international system of human rights protection. They set out nearly 70 international standards that constitute a common concept of human rights for men and women.

In independent Uzbekistan, the issue of women has risen to the level of state policy. In this sense, the rights and interests of women are reflected in more than 80 different legal acts. In particular, on the basis of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to increase the role of women in the state and social construction of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated March 2, 1995, the Chairman of the Women's Committee of Uzbekistan Deputy Chairman of the Women's Committee of the Republic of Karakalpakstan was awarded the status of Deputy Chairman of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Deputy Chairmen of the Women's Committees of the city of Tashkent and regions and districts. In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 25, 2004 "On additional measures to support the activities of the Women's Committee of Uzbekistan" women are appointed as advisers on religious-enlightenment and spiritual-moral education.

In 1995, the United Nations adopted the United Nations Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW), on the Protection of Motherhood, on the Political Rights of Women, and on Equal Values for Men and Women. has signed international conventions on equal incentives for labor, the Beijing Platform and the Action Plan. The main content of these international regulations is applied to the national legal system.

The Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women links the equal rights of men and women in politics to the following basic conditions. States Parties undertake to treat women equally as men:

- 1) voting in all elections and public referendums and election to all openly elected bodies;
- 2) participation in the formation and implementation of government policy and the implementation of state functions at all levels of government;
- 3) participation in the activities of non-governmental organizations and associations, dealing with issues of social and political life of the country;
- 4) guarantee the right of its government to represent itself at the international level and to participate in the activities of international organizations.

The Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action, adopted at the Beijing World Conference on Women, clearly identifies inequalities between women and men in 12 key areas of concern, including the separation of powers and directive decision-making at all levels. The Platform for Action acknowledges that many political parties and state structures still prevent women from participating in public life.

Even today, there is a lot of work being done by government agencies to eliminate inequality between women and men. The main purpose of the organization of consultative councils in government agencies is to create equal rights and opportunities for women and men in each labor collective, to protect their labor rights, to pay them a decent salary, to encourage them, to recommend them for leadership positions, as well as analysis of the work being done in this regard and the development of the necessary proposals.

This structure implements the following activities in accordance with the priorities and recommendations of the Republican Commission on Gender Equality:

- Provides suggestions on the implementation of state programs, national action plans and strategies to ensure equal rights and opportunities for women and men;
- Participates directly in the legal (gender-legal) examination of normative-legal and other internal normative acts adopted by the legal service in order to ensure gender equality;
- Study the status of benefits provided to women in the Labor Code of Uzbekistan and other applicable regulations, and prepare proposals on its results;
- Develops and submits to the legal service proposals on the elimination of gender inequality identified through the analysis of internal departmental documents;
- Monitors, evaluates the work process and develops and submits appropriate recommendations to management to address identified deficiencies;
- Ensures equal rights and opportunities for women and men;
- Ensures gender equality in interviews or other processes with candidates for employment, in the appointment of positions and positions by the employer, and in the formation of human resources;
- Ensures that talented, demanding and responsible women are recommended for leadership positions;
- Considers employees' complaints about violations of equal rights and opportunities for women and men;
- Carries out activities aimed at eliminating violence in the workplace and takes measures to prevent such incidents;
- Ensures gender equality in nominating and promoting state awards and badges;
- Prepares proposals for the organization of training on equal rights and opportunities for women and men;

- Makes proposals to the management on the creation of equal professional opportunities in the workforce, in particular, on the basis of regular free medical examinations of women and girls;
- Monitors the equal payment of salaries and other equivalent payments to women and men working in the same positions;
- Carries out propaganda and advocacy work to create a culture of gender equality;
- Collaborates with other organizations to ensure gender equality.

In particular, in order to prevent gender discrimination against women, the Commission on Gender Equality was established in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The main tasks of the Commission are to implement a unified state policy in the field of equal rights and opportunities for women and men, to participate in the development and implementation of state programs, national action plans and strategies in this area. Cooperation with international organizations, relevant bodies of foreign countries in the field of providing information to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, ensuring equal rights and opportunities for women and men and compliance with international standards in this regard.

The prohibition of gender discrimination in the exercise of legal rights and freedoms does not apply to certain social relations.

According to Article 5 of this law, the following are not considered discrimination on the basis of sex:

- ❖ Identify differences in the regulation of the relationship between childbearing and breastfeeding;
- ❖ Conscription in the manner prescribed by law;
- ❖ Take temporary special measures to ensure the implementation of gender policy;
- ❖ Features of reproductive health in the protection of women's and men's labor;
- ❖ Make recommendations on professional qualifications;
- ❖ Establishing differences in the regulation of conditions and conditions of detention, as well as other measures of legal influence.

Conclusions

Based on the above information, the following conclusions can be drawn. Every citizen of Uzbekistan, whether a woman or a man, who has set a strategic goal to build a strong civil society based on the rule of law, today, first of all, has the courage, social activism and responsibility. and a high legal culture is required. In the family, in the workplace, in the community, at various levels of government, in business and politics, men and women of our nation are equally responsible for the future of our country.

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